

THE TYPICAL MISTAKES OF UZBEK LEARNERS OF GERMAN

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Abstract. *When you learn foreign languages, you often make mistakes. Mistakes are a natural part of the learning process and should also be corrected so that the The student's language develops as mistake-free as possible and the mistakes are not in the Stay a foreign language. Mistakes in the learning process also mean that the learner Form hypotheses about language, what in my opinion means that they want to learn too.*

Keywords: correction, mistake, learning, teaching, German language, teacher.

ТИПИЧНЫЕ ОШИБКИ УЗБЕКОВ, ИЗУЧАЮЩИХ НЕМЕЦКИЙ ЯЗЫК

Аннотация. *Когда вы изучаете иностранные языки, вы часто делаете ошибки. Ошибки являются естественной частью процесса обучения, и их также следует исправлять, чтобы язык учащегося развивался как можно без ошибок, а ошибки не оставались на месте. Ошибки в процессе обучения также означают, что учащиеся формируют гипотезы о языке, что, на мой взгляд, означает, что они тоже хотят учиться.*

Ключевые слова: исправление, ошибка, обучение, обучение, немецкий язык, учитель.

INTRODUCTION

According to Corder mistakes are of particular concern for three different reasons: First are they helpful to the teacher in the sense that they convey to him how much of the Student has already learned and how much he still has to learn; second, inform the Researchers make mistakes about how languages are learned and what strategies are used when Learning to be used; third, the mistakes are special to the learner himself important because they function as learning tools that the learner hypotheses form about the language and these (sometimes flawed) hypotheses while learning check. So the third reason means that mistakes are a kind of can form a learning strategy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In addition to Corder, Kordes writes as follows: “Learners are there to make mistakes, researchers analyze and teachers correct them”. Teacher correct because they help their students through it, or because they think correcting is part of their role as a teacher. Koll Stobbe believes that “language learning is a risk that the Students enter”. So the role of the teacher is so important, because he helps and supports his students in language learning. It is also important that the teachers create a learning situation that is as “free from fear of mistakes” as possible, so that the encouraging students to take the risk of learning a language.

But before we get to that, think about this: How is learning a second language different from learning a first? There are many differences, but the most significant difference is that with a first language there is no interference from another language. An infant learning to speak for the first time is a blank slate—without any preconceived notions of how a language is supposed to work. That is definitely not the case for anyone who decides to learn a second language. An Uzbek speaker who is learning German must guard against the influence of Uzbek.

RESULTS

The first thing any language student has to accept is that there is no right or wrong way to construct a language. Uzbek is what it is; German is what it is. Arguing about a language's grammar or vocabulary is like arguing about the weather: you can't change it. If the gender of Haus is neuter (das), you can't arbitrarily change it to der. If you do, then you risk being misunderstood. The reason languages have a particular grammar is to avoid breakdowns in communication.

Mistakes Are Unavoidable. Even if you understand the concept of first-language interference, does that mean you'll never make a mistake in German? Of course not. And that leads us to a big mistake that many students make: Being afraid to make a mistake. Speaking and writing German is a challenge for any student of the language. But the fear of making a mistake can keep you from making progress. Students who don't worry so much about embarrassing themselves end up using the language more and making quicker progress.

1. Thinking in Uzbek

It's only natural that you'll think in English when you begin to learn another language. But the number one mistake made by beginners is thinking too literally and translating word-for-word. As you progress you need to start to "*think German*" more and more. Even beginners can learn to "think" in German phrases at an early stage. If you keep using Uzbek as a crutch, always translating from Uzbek to German, you're doing something wrong. You don't really know German until you start to "hear" it in your head. German doesn't always put things together like English.

2. Getting Genders Mixed Up

While languages such as French, Italian, or Spanish are content to have just two genders for nouns, German has three! Since every noun in German is either der, die, or das, you need to learn each noun with its gender. Using the wrong gender not only makes you sound stupid, it also can cause changes in meaning. It can be aggravating that any six-year-old in Germany can rattle off the gender of any common noun, but that's the way it is.

3. Case Confusion

If you don't understand what the "nominative" case is in Uzbek, or what a direct or indirect object is, then you're going to have problems with case in German. Case is usually indicated in German by "inflection": putting different endings on articles and adjectives. When der changes to den or dem, it does so for a reason. Not using the correct case is very likely to confuse people a lot!

4. Word Order

German word order (or syntax) is more flexible than Uzbek syntax and relies more on case endings for clarity. In German, the subject may not always come first in a sentence. In subordinate (dependent) clauses, the conjugated verb may be at the end of the clause.

6. Getting Prepositions Wrong

One of the easiest ways to spot a non-native speaker of any language is the misuse of prepositions. German and Uzbek often use different prepositions for similar idioms or expressions: Uzbek language does not have prepositional phrase. German also has two-way prepositions that can take two different cases (accusative or dative), depending on the situation.

8. Punctuation and Contractions

German punctuation and the use of the apostrophe is often different than in English. Possessives in German usually do not use an apostrophe. German uses contractions in many

common expressions, some of which use an apostrophe ("Wie geht's?") and some of which do not ("zum Rathaus"). Related to the prepositional hazards mentioned above are German prepositional contractions. Contractions such as am, ans, ins, or im can be possible pitfalls.

9. Those Pesky Capitalization Rules

German is the only modern language that requires the capitalization of all nouns, but there are other potential problems. For one thing, adjectives of nationality are not capitalized in German as they are in English. Partly due to German spelling reform, even Germans can have problems with spelling hazards like am besten or auf Deutsch. You can find the rules and a lot of hints for German spelling in our capitalization lesson and try our spelling quiz.

DISCUSSION

Phonetic and phonological mistakes.

Phonetic mistakes mean pronunciation mistakes and phonological mistakes Spelling mistakes - or spelling mistakes. There my work relates to the oral mistakes, I'll refer to that here concentrate on phonetic mistakes, i.e. pronunciation mistakes. Correcting pronunciation mistakes at the beginner level has a great one importance. The younger the learner is, the more capable he is, learn the pronunciation of a foreign language. If this mistake doesn't start to be corrected, it is more difficult to act on them later. The most important thing is there, a difference between the sounds in the mother tongue and those in the To do foreign language. This is most easily done when taught to learners where and how the sounds are formed, what e.g. by the position of the tongue in the mouth or by placing the hand on the neck can clarify. The rhythm and intonation of the foreign language should also be used be practiced, as these are different in almost all languages. That helps here Read aloud what the learner can practice at home. The sooner you get attention puts on pronunciation, the better it is learned.

Morphosyntactic mistakes.

Morphosyntactic mistakes are mistakes in the morphology (e.g. verb endings in the conjugation) or mistakes on the syntax level (e.g. word order in the sentence). Morphological mistakes can also occur in the area of the vocabulary, such as the plural formation of nouns. Often however, morphosyntactic mistakes relate to grammar. Grammatical mistakes can be those that the learner does if he hasn't the correct rule yet knows. Here the learner tries something new and forms hypotheses about the language, which he then tests through experiments. The formation of hypotheses about the target language leads to a growing awareness of the foreign language system. The learner needs help and an explanation from the teacher because he has the correct rules does not yet know the rules. A direct teacher correction is therefore required. Also learners can help each other by explaining the rules to each other if one knows them and others don't yet. Grammatical mistakes can also be those that the learner makes although he does should already know the correct shape. It may also still be the correct rule has not been fully understood or that the learner has since forgotten it has. In these cases the teacher can use non-verbal cues, such as through Hand signals for the rearrangement of words in the sentence, or signal the teacher can initiate selfcorrection, e.g. through metalanguage: "It's about Accusative". According to Kleppin the insertion of non-verbal cues is very easy for grammar mistakes, especially if the rules have already been discussed because the learner can react to these cues fairly easily.

CONCLUSION

When speaking freely, one should interrupt the utterance as little as possible, because then it is mainly about communication itself. Here it is then It makes more sense to collect the mistakes that have occurred first and only collect them after the discuss utterances.

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